

HeriTACE

Communication and Dissemination plan (version 2)

Deliverable D7.4

Version: N°1.0

DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.15656856](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15656856)

Authors: Marta Candidi (ACE), Swapna Saha (ACE)

**Funded by
the European Union**

Disclaimer

Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European union or the European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them. The content of this report reflects only the author's view. The European Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

Project information

Grant Agreement	n°101138672
Project Title	Future-proofing Heritage Townhouses by Optimising Comfort and Energy in Time and Space
Project Acronym	HeriTACE
Project Coordinator	Arnold Janssens, Ghent University
Project Duration	1 January 2024 - 31 December 2027 (48 months)

Deliverable information

Related Work Package	WP7: Communication & Dissemination
Related Task(s)	Task 7.1 Dissemination and communication plan
Lead Organisation	Architects' Council of Europe - ACE
Contributing Partner(s)	LGI, UGent
Due Date	30/06/2025
Submission Date	26/06/2025
Dissemination level	PU-Public

History

Date	Version	Submitted by	Reviewed by	Comments
23/06/25	1.0	Marta Candidi, ACE	Eline Himpe, UGent	Submitted

Table of contents

Executive Summary	6
1. Communication & Dissemination Strategy.....	9
1.1. Role of the consortium partners	10
1.2. Relationship with the other project activities	11
1.3. Key messages for C&D.....	15
1.3.1. Key message (long version)	15
1.3.2. Key message (short version)	16
2. Target groups and KPIs.....	17
3. Website and social media	19
3.1. HeriTACE Website.....	19
3.2. HeriTACE bi-annual newsletter.....	28
3.3. HeriTACE LinkedIn account	30
3.4. HeriTACE X account.....	31
3.5. HeriTACE Zenodo Community	32
4. Events.....	33
4.1. Participation in conferences / EU initiatives	33
4.2. Cluster activities with other projects	34
5. Activities reported on the F&T Portal	34
6. Conclusion.....	36
Annexes.....	37
A.1 Visual Identity.....	37
A.2 Leaflet.....	38
A.3 A0 Poster	39
A.4 Roll-up Poster.....	40
A.5 Newsletter	41
A.6 Press releases.....	42

List of figures

Figure 1 - Connection among the different WPs	12
Figure 2 - HeriTACE main target groups	17
Figure 3 - HeriTACE Website.....	19
Figure 4 - Website homepage after its publication.....	22
Figure 5 - Webpage on the project objectives and general information.....	23
Figure 6 - Webpage on the Consortium	24
Figure 7- Webpage on the HeriTACE network (sister and related projects, related initiatives)	25
Figure 8 - Heritage Townhouses webpage	26
Figure 9 - Reports webpage	26
Figure 10- Publications webpage	27
Figure 11 - News & Events webpage	27
Figure 12- Media Centre webpage.....	28
Figure 13- HeriTACE Newsletter #1	29
Figure 14- HeriTACE Newsletter #2	30
Figure 15 - HeriTACE LinkedIn page	31
Figure 16- Example of successful post on X (former Twitter).....	32
Figure 17- HeriTACE Zenodo community	33
Figure 18 - Communication activities reported on the F&T portal up to M18.....	34

List of tables

Table 1. List of public deliverables.....	12
Table 2 - List of channels, target groups and KPIs	17
Table 3. HeriTAGE LinkedIn profile numbers	30
Table 4 - Reported Communication activities.....	35
Table 5 - Reported dissemination activities	35
Table 6 - Main target groups reached	35

Executive Summary

This Communication and Dissemination Plan is intended for the consortium partners to ensure their participation in all the related activities, and for the European Commission to communicate the consortium's strategy and report on the activities carried out.

The HeriTACE project places great importance on dissemination and communication, as they are fundamental to reaching out to different target groups and presenting research findings to them. The communication and dissemination strategy varies for each category of stakeholders, but the core message and brand remain consistent across all activities.

This is the second version of the C&D Plan, which sets out the overall strategy and planned activities for the successful dissemination of the project's progress and results. It shows the steps taken in the first 18 months of the project, including: the project logo and visual identity applied to all project outputs to establish a recognisable brand identity; the production of a leaflet, and A0 poster and roll-up made available to the partners in the early phase of the project to support the project's identity and visibility during events; two social media accounts created on LinkedIn - with a focus on a professional audience - and X (former Twitter) - with a focus on a general audience, the events organised and attended on behalf of the project and the cluster activities undertaken with sister and related projects. It sets the path as well to move forward in the following months. Targets and key performance indicators (KPIs) are measured within the report to monitor the performance of the strategy.

This document is meant to be constantly updated throughout the project's lifespan with the status and progress from the partners on their actual dissemination activities. This is the second version (D7.4), followed by a third version due in M30 (D7.5) and a fourth and last version due in M48 (D7.7). The final version will be submitted at the end of the project, as a final report on all undertaken dissemination activities.

The C&D plan comprises:

1. The overall strategy at different level and the roles to undertake by each project partners;
2. The C&D content;
3. The list of target groups relevant for the project purposes;
4. The channels to use to reach those target groups;
5. The social media strategy and type of content;
6. Report on the C&D activities until M18 on the F&T portal;
7. The participation to conference and EU related events
8. The future steps
9. Annexes:
 - a. Visual Identity
 - b. Newsletter
 - c. Promotional materials
 - d. Press releases

Abbreviations and acronyms

Acronym	Description
AB	Advisory Board
C&D	Communication and Dissemination
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
F&T Portal	Funding and Tenders Portal (EU-portal)
GA	Grant Agreement
HEU	Horizon Europe

Glossary

Communication means 'Taking strategic and targeted measures for promoting the action itself and its results to a multitude of audiences, including the media and the public, and possibly engaging in a two-way exchange. This means to:

- Reach out to society as a whole
- Demonstrate how EU funding contributes to tackling societal challenges
- Strategically planned with pertinent messages, right medium and means.'¹

Dissemination means 'the public disclosure of the results by appropriate means, other than resulting from protecting or exploiting the results, including by scientific publications in any medium.

- Circulation of knowledge and results to the ones that can best make use of them
- Enabling the value of results to be potentially wider than the original focus
- Essential element of all good research practice and vital part of the project plan'²

¹ https://rea.ec.europa.eu/dissemination-and-exploitation_en

² https://rea.ec.europa.eu/dissemination-and-exploitation_en

1. Communication & Dissemination Strategy

The HeriTACE project established different communication materials and tools to showcase its results to the main identified stakeholders/target groups, including: 1) policy makers, 2) building design & conservation professionals, 3) building owners, local communities and civil society, 4) building material industry and HVAC industries/SMEs, 5) the academic world in education and research, 6) companies/contractors specialised in renovation of historical buildings. A detailed list of the Target Groups can be found in chapter 2.

This chapter focuses on the specific roles of the project partners, then lists the public deliverables of the project - which are essential to disseminate the project on a broader scale. Thereafter the content, i.e. the target message of HeriTACE is presented.

While chapter 2 introduces the target groups and chapter 3 the channels to reach them, the overall strategy can be summarised as follows:

Online tools and channels to build an active community:

- **Project website** published in M6, which is constantly updated with news, events, and general posts. The website is meant to be not just a simple archive of documents and activities; the website aims to demonstrate the feasibility of the holistic deep renovation approaches for climate-neutral historical neighbourhoods. Therefore, it takes a “marketing” approach by presenting its objectives, results, and key reports;
- **Social media channels** have been opened on [LinkedIn](#) and [X-former Twitter](#) since the beginning of the project. They have also been integrated into the website and are managed primarily by ACE and LGI, with contributions from all partners. A YouTube account has been opened to share videos on the project demos and overall objectives on a later stage.
- **A bi-annual newsletter** serving as a crucial media tool for informing the subscribers (partners and not) about the latest project news and driving traffic to the project website. On the newsletter the subscribers can find also relevant information and initiatives on heritage at EU scale

Events:

- At least **4 national and/or international events and workshops** to facilitate engagement with stakeholders and showcase project progress
- Participation in at least **12 conferences organised by third parties and EU initiatives** to communicate the project results at international/EU- scale conferences (e.g. in the fields of heritage, building energy renovation and energy systems, and HVAC), finding synergies with the EU institutions (e.g. EU sustainable energy week)
- **Clustering** and knowledge exchange are pursued between HeriTACE and [FutureHIST](#), which are sister projects funded under the same call and topic. The two projects have their own peculiar points of view regarding the renovation of existing buildings with historical value. At the same time, regular exchanges are ongoing with

related projects, such as [Caleche](#) and [Sincere](#) to engage in dissemination activities together.

Publications:

- Scientific publications are being produced and published in open-access journals and online repositories. They are available on Open-Access journals and [Zenodo](#), where the project has opened its own community. Partners' repositories will also be used to make publications accessible.
- Guidelines for designers and architects will be also produced in a form of booklet by the end of the project, providing informative design guidelines related to the project in a visually attractive form.

Communication materials:

- **Graphic material** such as a leaflet, an A0 poster and a roll-up poster have been developed for partners to share in occasion of events, conferences, workshops. They are also available on the website in the digital format.
- **A project video** will be produced by September 2025 to communicate the project objectives and vision to professionals in the sector, and of course the general public.
- **Public Learning module** for students and young professionals will be produced to spread the knowledge developed during the project among students and young professionals. The content of this video module will expose the innovative approach and technical features that have been developed.

The strategy will be regularly updated throughout the project's life. Partners will play an active role in promoting the project's communication channels and content to increase visibility and reach.

1.1. Role of the consortium partners

The **ACE** is in charge of coordinating all dissemination and communication activities with **LGI** leading some of the tasks. ACE is responsible for the C&D plan, the social media accounts, the newsletters. With the support of LGI, ACE will also develop the guidelines for designers and architects during the last phase of the project.

LGI is in charge of the visual identity of the project, the website, the promotional material, one video to be produced during the last phase of the project. Furthermore, LGI will have a key role in aligning the C&D activities with the exploitation strategy, that LGI is in charge of in T6.3.

Coordinator **UGent's** main role is to ensure the scientific and technical quality of communication and dissemination activities together with the partners responsible to provide the content. UGent follows up regularly with the activities conducted in WP7, mainly through the monthly meetings involving ACE and LGI, which have proven to be an effective organisational and communication channel. The coordinator also has the final say on the C&D material (both offline and online). Moreover, UGent supports ACE and LGI with the organisation of cluster activities to increase synergies between and the visibility of Horizon Europe and European Commission-supported actions

TalTech, in collaboration with **SINTEF**, **Sakret OU** and **DENYS** will have a major role in developing energy-efficient and durable building envelope solutions for heritage buildings in three phases: 1) matching technical solutions for heritage buildings considering the heritage value and physical behaviour; 2) development of façade retrofit solutions that reduce heat losses while safeguarding the hygrothermal performance and reduce maintenance; 3) quantify airtightness levels for case-study typologies, and develop improved fenestration systems.

UGent, TalTech, EURAC, ZH will optimise the comfort and IAQ in heritage townhouses in an energy-efficient way by developing and demonstrating smart HVAC concepts that safeguard the heritage value of townhouses; simulation-based design guidelines for optimal holistic renovation of heritage townhouses, balancing their heritage value with envelope and HVAC interventions, reducing the design cost in future projects; a set of optimised holistic renovation concepts for the heritage case studies with quantified performance.

KU Leuven, ZH, Builtwins BV, SWECO Belgium, SWECO Finland will propose clean energy supply concepts for historical buildings and neighbourhoods to investigate, develop, demonstrate and validate smartly controlled Renewable & Residual Energy Sources (R²ES)-based energy supply and exchange solutions for historical buildings, in line with heritage constraints.

UGent, SINTEF, NIKU, PoliMi, City of Ghent and **MKA** will develop a holistic and multi-scale renovation approach for heritage townhouses in historical neighbourhoods and validate a multi-dimensional assessment model for identifying the most appropriate deep energy retrofit solutions.

All partners are expected to actively participate in communication and dissemination activities by contributing to the project's newsletters, providing updates for the website and social media, and bring the promotional material at their own events and conferences. They are responsible as well of delivering high quality materials and inputs for the C&D activities where they are taking part into. They will also help spread the content through their own dissemination networks, channels, and networks. They are as well responsible of delivering high quality materials and inputs for the C&D activities they are involved in.

1.2. Relationship with the other project activities

Dissemination and communication are closely tied to all other project activities and progress, as they continuously contribute to all communication efforts, as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1 - Connection among the different WPs

As the project activities are interconnected with C&D, all public deliverables produced during the project will be indeed used to create dissemination content that reaches the target groups and will be published on HeriTACE website and Zenodo community page. The Table 1 lists all the project deliverables with a public dissemination level, including the partners leading and the due date.

Table 1. List of public deliverables

Deliverable n.	Title	Lead partner	Type	Due date
D1.1	Project Management Plan	UGent	R – Document, report	M3
D1.2	Data Management Plan (initial)	UGent	DMP – Data Management Plan	M6
D1.3	Data Management Plan (update)	UGent	DMP – Data Management Plan	M30
D1.4	Data Management Plan (final)	UGent	DMP – Data Management Plan	M48
D2.1	Building envelope characteristics	TalTech	R – Document, report	M12
D2.2	Energy Conservation measures inventory	TalTech	R – Document, report	M12
D2.4	Future-proof concept for interior retrofitting of wooden facades	SINTEF	DEM – Demonstrator, pilot, prototype	M30
D2.5	Improved historical window systems	UGent	DEM – Demonstrator, pilot, prototype	M24
D3.1	HVAC-concepts for heritage buildings	ZH	R – Document, report	M12
D3.2	Comfort and IAQ in heritage townhouses	ZH	R – Document, report	M18
D3.3	Baseline BES-models	UGent	Other	M24
D3.4	Smart ventilation strategies reducing	SINTEF	R – Document, report	M36

	moisture risks			
D3.5	Performance-based ventilation and control Strategies	UGent	R – Document, report	M36
D3.6	Ventilative cooling guide	EURAC	R – Document, report	M30
D3.7	Smart hybrid heating concepts	UGent	R – Document, report	M36
D3.8	Performance assessment of building envelope and HVAC concepts in heritage townhouses (initial)	UGent	R – Document, report	M40
D3.9	Performance assessment of building envelope and HVAC concepts in heritage townhouses (final)	UGent	R – Document, report	M48
D4.1	R ² ES-based energy supply concepts for heritage buildings in historical neighbourhoods	SWECO Finland	R – Document, report	M12
D4.3	Feasibility of heat recovery from unharvested local sources in heritage environments	SWECO Belgium	R – Document, report	M24
D4.4	GPU-based MPC solver	Builtwins BV	R – Document, report	M36
D4.5	MPC demonstration in historic building	Builtwins BV	R – Document, report	M36
D4.6	Building block MPC extensions	KU Leuven	R – Document, report	M42
D4.7	Performance assessment of R ² ES concepts in heritage townhouses in historical neighbourhoods (initial)	KU Leuven	R – Document, report	M40
D4.8	Performance assessment of R ² ES concepts in heritage townhouses in historical neighbourhoods (final)	KU Leuven	R – Document, report	M48
D5.1	Case-study selection at building and neighbourhood levels	UGent	R – Document, report	M6
D5.2	Cultural heritage analysis and value assessment	NIKU	R – Document, report	M18
D5.3	Cultural heritage building user and owner perspectives	NIKU	R – Document, report	M18
D5.4	Baseline scenarios	UGent	R – Document, report	M18
D5.5	Map of KPI	SINTEF	R – Document, report	M18
D5.6	Visualisation model to assess the visual impact of energy retrofitting solutions on the building heritage value	SINTEF	Other	M30

D5.7	Multidimensional model for the holistic and multi-scale assessment of heritage buildings	SINTEF	R – Document, report	M36
D5.8	Validation of the holistic and multi-scale assessment model	UGent	R – Document, report	M48
D6.1	Transdisciplinary processes for the holistic future-proofing of heritage buildings in neighbourhoods	POLIMI	R – Document, report	M48
D6.2	Policy advice report	POLIMI	R – Document, report	M48
D6.3	Customer services for early-stage design of neighbourhood energy systems	SWECO Finland	R – Document, report	M48
D6.4	Integrated and balanced design guidelines for heritage townhouses	UGent	R – Document, report	M48
D6.5	Early design tools for the feasibility assessment of innovative HVAC and energy Solutions	SWECO Belgium	R – Document, report	M48
D6.6	Technical guidelines for building the building envelope solutions	TalTech	R – Document, report	M42
D7.1	Communication and Dissemination plan (version 1)	ACE	R – Document, report	M6
D7.2	HeriTACE Visual Identity	LGI	Other	M6
D7.3	Website and social media	LGI	DEC –Websites, patent filings, videos, etc	M6
D7.4	Communication and Dissemination plan (version 2)	ACE	R – Document, report	M18
D7.5	Communication and Dissemination plan (version 3)	ACE	R – Document, report	M30
D7.6	Online and offline dissemination material (version 1)	ACE	DEC –Websites, patent filings, videos, etc	M30
D7.7	Communication and Dissemination plan (final version)	ACE	R – Document, report	M48
D7.8	Online and offline dissemination material (version 2)	ACE	DEC –Websites, patent filings, videos, etc	M48
D7.9	Guidelines for designers and architects	ACE	R – Document, report	M48

From the deliverables mentioned in Table 1, D3.2, D5.2, D5.3, D5.4, D5.5, and D7.4 will be uploaded on the website in the upcoming weeks as they are due in M18 (June 2025).

1.3. Key messages for C&D

The HeriTACE project proposes innovative solutions to future-proof heritage townhouses and historical neighbourhoods in three EU climate zones in a holistic way while preserving their heritage value. These solutions include a holistic assessment model and process and replicable optimal design approaches for the deep renovation of heritage townhouses. The integrated approaches are supported by innovations involving durable insulation and air tightness solutions, optimised and smart HVAC concepts and integrated R²ES-based energy supply solutions for historical buildings and neighbourhoods.

The following key messages have been developed to address different types of audiences, including the general public. They are used on the website and other communication tools such as online and offline promotional materials (leaflet, A0 poster, roll-up poster).

1.3.1. Key message (long version)

FUTURE-PROOFING HERITAGE BUILDINGS BY OPTIMISING COMFORT AND ENERGY IN TIME AND SPACE

HeriTACE is a collaborative initiative aimed at transforming heritage townhouse buildings into energy-efficient assets while preserving their historical integrity. Our transdisciplinary team, comprising research institutes, authorities, SMEs, and industry experts, is dedicated to developing innovative solutions for deep renovations of heritage townhouses. Through holistic assessments, optimal design approaches, durable insulation solutions, smart HVAC concepts, and integrated energy supply solutions, HeriTACE ensures a sustainable future for historical neighbourhoods. Join us in realizing the EU Green Deal and New European Bauhaus objectives by navigating the future of heritage conservation and energy efficiency.

Holistic and multi-scale approach

The HeriTACE project addresses the complex challenge of transitioning historical European cities towards climate neutrality while preserving their cultural heritage and identity. Its mission is to create a sustainable, inclusive living environment in alignment with the EU Green Deal and New European Bauhaus.

*HeriTACE aims to develop and demonstrate a **holistic renovation approach** for heritage buildings, accounting for (1) the heritage value of the building and its durable and high quality preservation for the future generations, (2) the indoor environmental quality to realise a healthy and comfortable environment exactly where and when the users need it, ensuring better living conditions; (3) the overall energy-efficiency of the heritage building and its readiness to decouple from fossil fuels; (4) the increased use of Renewable and Residual Energy Sources in the building and its improved integration in the local energy grids; (5) the overall sustainability, efficient and circular material use, reducing the renovation environmental impact; and (6) the increased life-time cost effectiveness and affordability. To achieve this, the renovation approach integrates and optimises **solutions at three scales**: the building and system components, the building, and the neighbourhood. Well-considered and targeted measures at each of these scales are part of an optimisation over all the scales.*

Objectives

- Develop a replicable **holistic assessment model and standardised transdisciplinary processes** to create a holistic vision and plan on the renovation requirements for heritage townhouses in historical neighbourhoods that meets both heritage conservation and climate goals and is supported by conservation and climate authorities.
- Develop optimal and integrated design approaches for deep renovation of heritage townhouses within historical neighbourhoods.
- Provide durable insulation and air tightness solutions for building envelope renovation, respecting heritage values and traditional building technology
- Develop optimized and smart-controlled HVAC concepts to improve comfort and indoor air quality in historical townhouses, reducing energy demand by 60%.
- Develop integrated R²ES-based energy supply solutions, maximising the share of local R²ES in heritage buildings within historical neighbourhoods and and promote collective energy supply systems on a neighbourhood level, where feasible.
- Vision for Sustainability: HeriTACE aims to develop a balanced holistic vision and plan for heritage buildings and neighbourhoods, aligning heritage preservation with environmental goals, and providing transition roadmaps and policies.
- Deep Renovation Challenges: The project addresses sub-optimal renovation practices, especially for historical buildings, by advocating for efficient and standardized approaches to ensure coordinated work execution.
- Energy Efficiency and Integration: HeriTACE focuses on significant energy demand reduction and local Renewable and Residual Energy Sources (R²ES) integration, addressing challenges in applying energy-efficient (collective) technologies and improving Indoor Environmental Quality (IEQ).
- Holistic Approach: Emphasizing physically sound and durable insulation solutions, optimization of HVAC systems, and aesthetically integrated R²ES solutions at the neighbourhood level to enhance efficiency and inclusivity.
- Collaborative Solutions: HeriTACE promotes collaboration among stakeholders to develop high-quality solutions for heritage conservation, aiming to deliver replicable models and standards for sustainable energy transitions in historical neighbourhoods.

1.3.2. Key message (short version)

FUTURE-PROOFING HERITAGE BUILDINGS BY OPTIMISING COMFORT AND ENERGY IN TIME AND SPACE

Our transdisciplinary team, comprising research institutes, authorities, SMEs, and industry experts, is dedicated to developing innovative solutions for deep renovations of heritage townhouses. Through holistic assessments, optimal design approaches, durable insulation solutions, smart HVAC concepts, integrated energy supply solutions and the use of renewable and residual energy sources, HeriTACE ensures a sustainable future for historical neighbourhoods.

2. Target groups and KPIs

As previously mentioned in the C&D strategy (chapter 1), the following target groups have been identified as essential for the success of the HeriTACE project:

Figure 2 - HeriTACE main target groups

Table 2 gives an overview of the communication tools and channels that will be adapted to each target audience. Quantified targets have been set to measure the impact and evaluate the effectiveness of the project's main communication and dissemination tools and channels. If the targets listed are not achieved, corrective actions will be implemented to ensure success and reported on the next version of the C&D plan.

Table 2 - List of channels, target groups and KPIs

Channel	Purpose	Target audience	KPIs	Impacts of KPIs
Project website	Main channel. Provide project information and latest updates in an interactive & user-friendly format	All target audiences, general public	10 000 visits by the end of the project	Wide scale dissemination of project key messages, public results & news.
Social media (Twitter and LinkedIn)	Provide project updates, news and insights and build an online community	All target audiences (Twitter mostly for the general public; LinkedIn mostly for professionals)	Combined number of followers 650	Increased awareness of the importance of historical building renovations; Engagement of stakeholders & dissemination of key results

Newsletters	Inform stakeholders of project progress, news & events of interest	All target audiences	150 subscribers by the end of the project	Dissemination and increased awareness of project results
National and/or international events and workshops / EU projects	Facilitate engagement with stakeholders and showcase project progress	Policy Makers, Building Design and Renovation Professionals, The Academic world - Education and Research, companies	4 workshops or project events (20-30 attendees)	Increased awareness and increased engagement with stakeholders
Guidelines for designers and architects (booklet)	Provide informative design guidelines related to the project in a visually attractive way.	specialized in renovation of historical buildings/ contractors, Building Material Industry and HVAC Industry/SMEs	400 views by M36	Increased understanding of new methods and tools for historical building renovation; dissemination of guidelines from the project's results
Scientific publications and non-scientific (technical/ specialist journals, newsletters)	Communicating the project results to the scientific community, Publications via ICOMOS, WTA Int., ACE, REHVA, Eurocities, Energy-cities, culturalheritageinaction.eu, historic-towns, Europa Nostra, BuildUP		at least 10 open access scientific publications/ at least 8 newsletter items	Sharing knowledge of new methods and tools for historical building renovation with the scientific and R&D community and Academia.
Participation in conferences organised by third parties and EU initiatives	Communicating the project results at international/EU-scale conferences (e.g. in the fields of heritage, building energy renovation and energy systems, HVAC), finding synergies with the EU institutions (e.g. EU sustainable energy week)		Project represented in at least 12 conferences, EC initiatives and events, commercial fairs	Increased awareness and increased engagement with stakeholders and networking opportunities
Project video	Communicating the project objectives and vision to professionals in the	All target audiences.	At least 250 views	Wide scale dissemination of project objectives and outcomes

	sector but also general public			
--	--------------------------------	--	--	--

Besides the key target groups and the general public, the HeriTACE project is establishing an Advisory Board that will play an important role in supporting the project outcomes. The AB members are professionals in the field of heritage and energy efficiency in buildings, including representatives from local and regional heritage agencies in the partners countries (e.g. Flanders Heritage Agency, Lombardy Heritage Agency), local and regional governments working on the energy transition, heritage conservation advisors/experts, architects, engineering offices, building industry (e.g. Renson), professional building owners and investors, research...

3. Website and social media

Various C&D channels ensure a good visibility of the project towards the identified target groups and general public. These include the HeriTACE Website, the social media accounts (LinkedIn and X), the bi-annual newsletter, the HeriTACE Zenodo community.

3.1. HeriTACE Website

The HeriTACE website has been online since M6 (see Figure 3).

Figure 3 - HeriTACE Website

The website is structured into the following main pages and subpages:

- **Homepage**, giving a glimpse of the project and the case studies, countries/ climate zones, and duration, and containing the form to subscribe to the project newsletter and a preview of the news and events;
- **About**, containing further information on the project, the consortium, and the related initiatives and projects (such as the sister project FutureHIST and other HEU projects involving heritage buildings);
- **Heritage townhouses within historical neighbourhoods.**, which will provide more information on the typologies of buildings and neighbourhoods selected as case studies in the future months;
- **Results**, including the public deliverables and publications, as well as the promotional material;
- **News and event**, containing all events and initiatives in which the HeriTACE project will be involved;
- **Media Centre**, containing HeriTACE visual identity such as logo, poster, rollup, leaflet and leaflet (digital version)

The header displays four icons linking to LinkedIn, X, YouTube and the project email. Furthermore, a footer on all pages showcases the EU flag and a disclaimer indicating the project GA number.

The website had 7644 visitors (June 2025) since its launch. The most visited pages are:

- Home (873)
- The project (749)
- News & events (740)

Users come mainly from USA, Belgium, France and Germany.

Compared to the first version, a new main page has been added in M12: **Media Center**, which now included the promotional materials, previously under "resources". "Resources" has been replaced by **Results**, including "**Reports**" and "**Publications**" as subpages.

ACE is currently preparing a reorganisation of the website in order to better explain the scope and objectives of the project and put into the spotlight the different technological innovations that are being researched and implemented in the project.

The launch of the restructured website is expected in September 2025 (M20) and will be included in the following version of this deliverable.

The screenshot shows the HeriTACE website homepage. At the top, there is a navigation bar with the HeriTACE logo on the left and menu items: ABOUT, HERITAGE TOWNHOUSES, RESOURCES, and NEWS & EVENTS. On the right of the navigation bar are social media icons for X, LinkedIn, and Email.

Future-proofing Heritage Buildings by Optimising Comfort and Energy in Time and Space

Our transdisciplinary team, comprising research institutes, authorities, SMEs, and industry experts, is dedicated to **developing innovative solutions for deep renovations of heritage townhouses**. Through holistic assessments, optimal design approaches, durable insulation solutions, smart HVAC concepts, and integrated energy supply solutions and the use of renewable and residual energy sources, **HeriTACE ensures a sustainable future for historical neighborhoods**.

17 Partners	6 Countries	48 Months
----------------	----------------	--------------

[Learn more](#)

Our cities

MANTOVA

The bottom section of the page features a large image of the Mantova cityscape, with the word "MANTOVA" overlaid in large, bold, orange letters. Below the image is a progress indicator consisting of four circles, with the first one filled in orange.

Figure 4 - Website homepage after its publication

The screenshot displays the HeriTACE website with a navigation bar at the top containing 'ABOUT', 'HERITAGE TOWNHOUSES', 'RESOURCES', and 'NEWS & EVENTS', along with social media icons for X, LinkedIn, and Facebook. The main content is organized into several sections:

- The Project:** A header section with a background image of a row of historic townhouses.
- Our Mission:** A section with a paragraph describing the project's goal to transform heritage townhouses into energy-efficient assets while preserving their historical integrity. It also includes a sub-section titled 'Holistic and multi-scale approach' and a photograph of a yellow wooden townhouse.
- Objectives:** A central section featuring five colored boxes, each with an icon and the text: 'Develop a holistic model and standard processes for renovating heritage townhouses in historical areas.' Below these boxes is a list of key project goals:
 - Vision for Sustainability:** HeriTACE aims to develop a balanced vision and plan for heritage buildings and neighborhoods, aligning heritage preservation with environmental goals and providing transition roadmaps and policies.
 - Deep Renovation Challenges:** The project addresses sub-optimal renovation practices, especially for historical buildings, by advocating for efficient and standardized approaches to ensure coordinated execution of works.
 - Energy Efficiency and Integration:** HeriTACE focuses on significant energy demand reduction and the integration of local renewable and flexible Energy Sources (RES), addressing challenges in applying energy-efficient technologies and improving Indoor Environmental Quality (IEQ).
 - Holistic Approach:** Emphasizing physically sound and durable insulation solutions, optimization of HVAC systems, and aesthetically integrated RES solutions at the neighborhood level to enhance efficiency and inclusivity.
 - Collaborative Solutions:** HeriTACE promotes collaborations among stakeholders to develop high-quality solutions for heritage conservation, aiming to deliver replicable models and blueprints for sustainable energy transitions in historical neighborhoods.
- Our Consortium:** A section displaying logos for partner organizations: NIJKU, POLITECNICO MILANO 1863, ghent, GHEENT UNIVERSITY, TAL TECH, KU LEUVEN, IGI, SWECO, SAKRET, and DENYS.
- Footer:** A red button labeled 'Subscribe to HeriTACE news'.

Figure 5 - Webpage on the project objectives and general information

Figure 6 - Webpage on the Consortium

Figure 7- Webpage on the HeriTACE network (sister and related projects, related initiatives)

Figure 8 - Heritage Townhouses webpage

Figure 9 - Reports webpage

Figure 10- Publications webpage

Figure 11 - News & Events webpage

Figure 12- Media Centre webpage

3.2. HeriTACE bi-annual newsletter

The newsletter has been set up on Mailchimp and is meant to be sent out every six months to promote the project's achievements, events, and publications, as well as EU-scale initiatives relevant to the HeriTACE audience (call for papers, conferences on heritage buildings, EC policies on cultural heritage).

- The first newsletter was sent out in June 2024 (M6 - Figure 13). Unfortunately, the number of subscribers is currently low (88 subscribers) as it was possible to promote it only when the website was fully online (M6 - beginning of June 2024).
- The second newsletter has been sent out in January 2025 (M12 - Figure 14), reaching 66 people.
- The 3rd Newsletter is planned for Summer 2025 (M19-20).

The KPI to reach for newsletter subscribers is 150 people.

[View this email in your browser](#)

HeriTACE 1st newsletter - June 2024

Dear readers,

Welcome to this first issue of the HeriTACE newsletter. Through this and future issues, we aim to inform you of the progress and findings of the HeriTACE research project.

Funded under the Horizon Europe framework, HeriTACE is short for 'Future-proofing Heritage townhouses by optimizing comfort and energy in Time and spACE'. The project started in January 2024 and will run until the end of 2027.

The HeriTACE project targets heritage townhouses pre-dating 1945 in three climate zones and within four partner countries: Belgium, Norway, Estonia, and Italy. These typologies cover single and multi-family buildings, and represent a small but significant share of the building stock in EU historical cities. The transition to climate neutrality is particularly challenging for those cities, as they aim to safeguard their cultural heritage and identity while enhancing their overall performance.

The HeriTACE project brings together a transdisciplinary team (photo above) of research institutes, authorities, SMEs, and industry experienced in design, technology, and policymaking in the domains of conservation, buildings and energy.

We wish you a pleasant reading and hope you find the information useful.

Arnold Janssens, UGent, Coordinator of the HeriTACE project

News from HeriTACE

Figure 13- HeriTACE Newsletter #1

Dear readers,

At the start of the New Year, the second HeriTACE newsletter arrives!

In this edition we introduce the case-study neighbourhoods in Ghent (Belgium), Trondheim (Norway), Tallinn (Estonia) and Mantova (Italy) and a set of archetypes for the heritage townhouses that is representative for the respective cities and countries. HeriTACE develops optimal and holistic renovation approaches for future-proofing these buildings for the sustainable energy transition, while safeguarding their cultural heritage value. To achieve this, the renovation approach integrates and optimizes solutions at three scales: the building and system components, the building and the neighbourhood.

Figure 14- HeriTACE Newsletter #2

3.3. HeriTACE LinkedIn account

The [HeriTACE LinkedIn profile](#) numbers are summed up in the table 3 and reflect the status as per June 2025. The followers include architects, engineers, experts in energy efficiency, experts in heritage buildings, researchers, and representatives for the EC.

Table 3. HeriTAGE LinkedIn profile numbers

Followers	357
Unique visitors (last 12 months)	358
Page views (last 12 months)	732
Overall impressions (last 12 months)	1,416

The KPI for social media channels is set for a combined number of 650 followers, so we are confident that we will reach this target by the end of the project.

Figure 15 - HeriTACE LinkedIn page

3.4. HeriTACE X account

The [HeriTACE X account](#) has **39 followers**, including H2020/HEU projects. The other statistics for X are no longer available due to the latest updates of the app.

The consideration about the LinkedIn KPIs can be applied to X, with the target being the total number of followers of LinkedIn and X combined. However, we find that LinkedIn's reach is broader, and it is clearly a better channel to communicate the project's news and results.

Figure 16- Example of successful post on X (former Twitter)

In terms of social media campaigns, a first one has been running to introduce all the project partners and concluded in February 2025.

The following months will be dedicated to the realisation of the promotional video that will highlight the objectives and the scope of the project. At the same time, the second communication campaign will start running: after having presented the consortium, we will focus this time on the research and technology partners. Each of them will engage with the audience in the form of short videos to explain the innovation they are working on, the challenges and the future perspectives regarding historical buildings. The video interviews have been recorded in occasion of the Consortium Meeting held in Tallin at the beginning of April 2025.

3.5. HeriTACE Zenodo Community

[Zenodo](https://zenodo.org) (<https://zenodo.org>) is an open repository for all scholarship, enabling researchers from all disciplines to share and preserve their research outputs, regardless of size or format. It is free to upload and free to access, and it makes scientific outputs of all kinds citable, shareable and discoverable for the long term.³

The UGent coordinator has established a HeriTACE community page on Zenodo. This page will serve as a repository for the project's scientific publications and relevant reports, ensuring a lasting impact even after the project's conclusion.

³ [https://www.openaire.eu/zenodo-guide#:~:text=Zenodo%20\(https%3A%2F%2Fzenodo.org,regardless%20of%20size%20or%20format.](https://www.openaire.eu/zenodo-guide#:~:text=Zenodo%20(https%3A%2F%2Fzenodo.org,regardless%20of%20size%20or%20format.)

The community includes so far (M18) **9 publications**, all open access: 8 project deliverables and 1 poster.

<https://zenodo.org/communities/heritace/>

Figure 17- HeriTACE Zenodo community

4. Events

4.1. Participation in conferences / EU initiatives

During the last 18 months of the project, HeriTACE has been presented in the following EU initiatives:

- Salone Internazionale del Restauro, Milan, May 2025 – presentation of the project during the Clust-ER session by Alessia Buda (PoliMi).
- Presentation of HeriTACE project at the Cultural Heritage & Tourism Working Group Meeting (hosted at ERRIN - European Regions Research and Innovation Network), Brussels, April 2025, SINTEF.
- The 5th International Conference on Energy Efficiency in Historic Buildings, Austria, October 2024 by Luca Maton (UGent) and Alexandra Troi (Eurac).
- Sustainable Places 2024 Conference, Luxembourg, September 2024 - session on 'Scalable and Resource-Efficient Solutions for Cultural Heritage' organised by the Caleche project by the coordinator Prof. Arnold Janssens (UGent).
- Flemish Heat Pump Symposium, Brussels, September 2024 - session "Sustainable Heat for Cities", UGent, Stad Gent and KU Leuven.
- International Conference on Sustainable Development of Energy, Water and Environment, Rome, September 2024, KU Leuven.

HeriTACE partners will be present as well at the SINCERE project session in the framework of the conference on Cultural Heritage and New Technologies that will take place in November 2025 in Vienna. The project is currently applying to other conference and events, and its participation is envisioned for the following months.

4.2. Cluster activities with other projects

HeriTACE is now working in close collaboration with the sister project FuturHist. The coordinators and the Communication and Dissemination leaders and partners of both projects have had already 3 coordination meetings to discuss the objectives of the respective projects and explore possible synergies and connections. Regular meetings are being planned, especially to discuss the joint participation to dissemination events and to plan a series of webinars focusing on the challenges and solutions of both projects.

5. Activities reported on the F&T Portal

Every six months, regular reporting on the forecast of planned and undertaken C&D activities for each consortium partner takes place. All activities have also been reported in the F&T portal communication/dissemination section. A screenshot of this is included below, giving a glimpse of the 81 C&D activities undertaken by the consortium partners from M1 to M18 (January 2024 to June 2025) and 2 more detailed table showing the communication and dissemination activities and the most reached target groups.

The screenshot shows the 'Project Continuous Report' interface. At the top, there is a progress bar with various icons representing different project metrics. Below this, a table titled 'Communications Activities' lists 81 activities. Each row includes the communication activity name, a description, the target audience, the communication channel, the outcome, and the status.

Communication Activity Name	Description	Who? Target audience	How? Communication channel	Outcome	Status	Actions
ACE - ACE Info Newsletter LinkedIn post 30.07.2024	LinkedIn post about ACE Info Summer Newsletter	Industry, business partners	Social media	680 People reached.	Delivered	X
ACE - ACE Info Newsletter 30.07.2024	ACE Info Summer Newsletter July 2024 about	Industry, business partners	Newsletter	16000 people reached	Delivered	X
SINTEP - Hvordan isolere verneverdig trehus?	An outreach to ask for old building materials	Citizens, industry, business partners, National authorities, Local authorities, Regional authorities, Civil society	Press release	Supply of old building materials and c	Ongoing	X
KULeuven - Conference presentation, 12.09.2024	Presenting a study under HeriTACE framework	Research communities	Event (conference, meeting, workshop, internet debate, round	Reached 600 people	Delivered	X
ACE - HeriTACE Flyers handed out 13.09.2024	ACE organized an event in Palma de Mallorca	Industry, business partners	Print materials (brochure, leaflet, posters, stickers, banners, e	31 people reached out	Delivered	X
KULeuven - LinkedIn post, 24.09.2024	LinkedIn post on conference paper on persona	Civil society	Social media	Reached 1254 people	Delivered	X
UGent - Stakeholder Meeting - 26/09/2024	Meeting with expert of the Flemish Heritage A	Regional authorities	Event (conference, meeting, workshop, internet debate, round	1 key stakeholder input/feedback gat!	Delivered	X
ACE - ACE Info Newsletter X post 30.07.2024	ACE Info summer Newsletter X post featuring I	Industry, business partners	Social media	168 people reached.	Delivered	X
Sweco BE - LinkedIn post 13.12.2024	Meet the partners Linked-in post	Citizens, industry, business partners	Social media	2461 views	Delivered	X
ACE LinkedIn report 23.10.2024	HeriTACE LinkedIn post, was shared through ACE	Industry, business partners	Social media	186 people reached out	Delivered	X
BT - HeriTACE project on Builtwins website	The HeriTACE project has been added on the B	Industry, business partners	Website	Reached website visitors	Delivered	X
UGent - Sustainable Places 2024 - 23.09.2024	UGent presented the HeriTACE project on the	Research communities, EU Institutions, Industry, business partners, National authorities, Specific end user communities	Event (conference, meeting, workshop, internet debate, round	30 participants reached	Delivered	X
UGent - Stakeholder meeting - 5/12/2025	Meeting with company (project developer spa	Industry, business partners	Event (conference, meeting, workshop, internet debate, round	1 stakeholder input/feedback	Delivered	X
ACE - LinkedIn report on HeriTACE website 20.06	ACE made a LinkedIn report from ACE's Linked	Industry, business partners	Social media	294 people reached out.	Delivered	X
ACE - Sustainable Place 2024 Participation 23.09	ACE delegates participated in the Sustainable	Research communities	Print materials (brochure, leaflet, posters, stickers, banners, e	400 people reached out.	Delivered	X
ACE - HeriTACE Flyers handed out 17.09.2024	At the ERIN EU Design Days meeting, the Her	Civil society	Print materials (brochure, leaflet, posters, stickers, banners, e	50 people reached out	Delivered	X
UGent - HeriTACE leaflets on AIVC2024-conference	HeriTACE leaflets were put on display in the e	Research communities, Industry, business partners, National authorities	Exhibition	Information provided to 184 participar	Delivered	X
UGent - architecture dept presentation -20/09/2024	Presentation of the HeriTACE project to the U	Research communities, Specific end user communities	Event (conference, meeting, workshop, internet debate, round	200 stakeholders reached	Delivered	X
SWECO-FI 20.9.2024	Meeting with city of Helsinki about energy imp	Local authorities	Event (conference, meeting, workshop, internet debate, round	4 people reached	Delivered	X
ACE - HeriTACE flyers handed out 18.10.2024	HeriTACE flyers were distributed during the ev	Research communities, Industry, business partners, Local authorities	Print materials (brochure, leaflet, posters, stickers, banners, e	29 people reached out	Delivered	X
SWECO-FI meeting 17.9.2024	Meeting about district level energy systems wi	Research communities	Event (conference, meeting, workshop, internet debate, round	Reached 5 people	Delivered	X
UGent - Interview with students 01_04_2025	Interview with students architectural engineer	Citizens, Civil society	Interview	4 students directly reached, 400 stuade	Delivered	X
KULeuven - IRP Symposium, 18.09.2024	Presentation of the HeriTACE project during th	Industry, business partners	Event (conference, meeting, workshop, internet debate, round	reached 180 people	Delivered	X

Figure 18 - Communication activities reported on the F&T portal up to M18

Table 4 - Reported Communication activities

Activity per type	Number
Exhibition	2
Social Media	16
Website	1
Newsletter	3
Event	25
Press release	1
Interview	2
Print materials	11
Media Article	2

Table 5 - Reported dissemination activities

Activity per type	Number
Meeting	3
Conference	5
Education & Training	5
Collaboration with other EU-funded projects	3

Table 6 - Main target groups reached

Target group	Number of activities
Industry	36
Innovators	5
EU Institutions	4
National authorities	8
Regional authorities	7
Local authorities	10
Civil society	12
Citizens	4
Specific end user communities	12
International organisations	4
Research communities	33

6. Conclusion

The report outlines the overall strategy and planned activities for effectively sharing the progress and results of the HeriTACE project. Communication and dissemination are ongoing processes that occur at all stages of the project, rather than being a one-time effort. As a result, this document will be regularly updated throughout the project's duration to include reports from partners on their planned and actual dissemination activities.

All activities carried out by the consortium up to M18 (June 2025) have been included in this report. Additionally, the report includes details of the various dissemination materials and channels that have been established.

It is recommended to all partners to use the visual identity guidelines and follow the strategy outlined in this deliverable. This involves correctly using the project name, logo, colour palette, templates, and acknowledging HEU funding.

Annexes

A.1 Visual Identity

Include elements from D7.2

A.2 Leaflet

Our transdisciplinary team is dedicated to developing **innovative solutions for deep renovations of heritage townhouses**.

Through holistic assessments, optimal design approaches, durable insulation solutions, integrated energy supply solutions and the use of renewable and residual energy sources, **HeriTACE ensures a sustainable future for historical neighborhoods**.

OUR OBJECTIVES

An overall holistic renovation approach for heritage townhouses:

- Holistic assessment model and transdisciplinary processes to create a holistic vision and plans
- Optimal and integrated design approaches, replicable through standardised guidelines

Specific innovations for heritage townhouses in 4 historical cities:

- Durable insulation and air tightness solutions
- Optimised and smart controlled HVAC concepts
- Integrated local RES based energy supply solutions

4 CASE STUDIES CITIES

A.3 A0 Poster

FUTURE-PROOFING HERITAGE BUILDINGS BY OPTIMISING COMFORT AND ENERGY IN TIME AND SPACE

HeriTACE

✉ heritace@ugent.be ✖ HeriTACEproject
🌐 www.heritace.eu 📌 HeriTACE

Our transdisciplinary team is dedicated to developing **innovative solutions for deep renovations of heritage townhouses**. Through holistic assessments, optimal design approaches, durable insulation solutions, smart HVAC concepts, and integrated energy supply solutions and the use of renewable and residual energy sources, **HeriTACE ensures a sustainable future for historical neighborhoods**.

An overall holistic renovation approach for heritage townhouses:

- Holistic assessment model and transdisciplinary processes to create a holistic vision and plans
- Optimal and **integrated design approaches**, replicable through standardised guidelines

Specific innovations for heritage townhouses in 4 historical cities:

- Durable insulation and air tightness solutions
- Optimised and smart controlled HVAC concepts
- Integrated local R²ES based energy supply solutions

6 PARTNER COUNTRIES

17 PARTNERS

2024-2028

4.5 M€ BUDGET

TRONDHEIM

TALLINN

GHENT

MANTOVA

Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European union or the European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

A.4 Roll-up Poster

HeriTACE

FUTURE-PROOFING HERITAGE BUILDINGS BY OPTIMISING COMFORT AND ENERGY IN TIME AND SPACE

6
PARTNER COUNTRIES

17
PARTNERS

2024
2028

4.5
MC BUDGET

Our transdisciplinary team is dedicated to developing **innovative solutions for deep renovations of heritage townhouses**. Through holistic assessments, optimal design approaches, durable insulation solutions, smart HVAC concepts, and integrated energy supply solutions and the use of renewable and residual energy sources, **HeriTACE ensures a sustainable future for historical neighborhoods.**

 heritace@ugent.be

 [HeriTACEproject](#)

 www.heritace.eu

 [HeriTACE](#)

Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

A.5 Newsletter

A.6 Press releases

<https://www.sintef.no/en/projects/2024/heritace/>

Our services > Projects >

Norsk / English

[Contact us](#) |
 [Our services](#) |
 [Career](#) |
 [Research areas](#) ▼ |
 [All about SINTEF](#) ▼

PROJECT

HeriTACE

A transdisciplinary project addressing the deep energy renovation of heritage buildings.

Contact person

Nicola Lolli
 Senior Research Scientist
 +47 45 06 33 20
nicola.lolli@sintef.no

20. February 2024

The HeriTACE project brings together a transdisciplinary team of research institutes, authorities, SMEs, and industry experienced in design, technology, and policymaking in the domains of conservation, buildings and energy.

A significant increase in deep renovations of heritage buildings has the potential to lead to effective energy demand reductions and readiness for the transition to Renewable and Residual Energy Sources (RES).

HeriTACE proposes innovative technical solutions, integrated into a holistic and multi-scale renovation approach, by developing and validating:

1. A replicable holistic assessment model and standardised processes to create a holistic vision and plan on the renovation requirements for heritage townhouses in historical neighbourhoods.
2. Optimal and integrated design approaches for the deep renovation of heritage townhouses, with well-considered, targeted and minimal invasive renovation measures.
3. Durable insulation and air tightness solutions for the renovation of building envelopes, respecting their heritage values and traditional